

Reproducible Bibliometric Script (R + bibliometrix)

This document provides a reproducible R script for the bibliometric analysis.

R Script

```
# =====  
# Reproducible bibliometric workflow (R) using bibliometrix  
# Project: IRM maturity models (SLR)  
# =====  
  
library(bibliometrix)  
library(dplyr)  
library(stringr)  
library(readr)  
library(ggplot2)  
  
dir.create("outputs", showWarnings = FALSE)  
dir.create("outputs/figures", showWarnings = FALSE)  
dir.create("outputs/tables", showWarnings = FALSE)  
  
scopus_bib <- "data/scopus.bib"  
wos_bib <- "data/wos.bib"  
  
M_scopus <- convert2df(file = scopus_bib, dbsource = "scopus", format = "bibtex")  
M_wos <- convert2df(file = wos_bib, dbsource = "wos", format = "bibtex")  
  
M <- mergeDbSources(M_scopus, M_wos, remove.duplicated = TRUE)  
  
results <- biblioAnalysis(M, sep = ";")  
S <- summary(results, k = 10, pause = FALSE)  
  
pdf("outputs/figures/main_info.pdf")  
plot(results)  
dev.off()  
  
pdf("outputs/figures/wordcloud.pdf")  
wordcloud(M, field = "DE")  
dev.off()  
  
pdf("outputs/figures/thematic_map.pdf")  
thematicMap(M, field="ID", n=250, minfreq=1)  
dev.off()  
  
write.csv(M, "outputs/merged_dataset.csv", row.names = FALSE)  
writeLines(capture.output(sessionInfo()), "outputs/sessionInfo.txt")
```